

Soft biomimetic nanoconfinement promotes amorphous water over ice

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Abstract

Water is a ubiquitous liquid with unique physicochemical properties, whose nature has shaped our planet and life as we know it. Water in restricted geometries has different properties than in bulk. Confinement can prevent low-temperature crystallization of the molecules into a hexagonal structure and thus create a state of amorphous water. To understand the survival of life at subzero temperatures, it is essential to elucidate this behaviour in the presence of nanoconfining lipidic membranes. Here we introduce a family of synthetic lipids with designed cyclopropyl modifications in the hydrophobic chains that exhibit unique liquid-crystalline behaviour at low temperature, which

enables the maintenance of amorphous water down to ~ 10 K due to nanoconfinement. The combination of experiments and molecular dynamics simulations unveils a complex lipid-water phase diagram in which bicontinuous cubic and lamellar liquid crystalline phases that contain subzero liquid, glassy or ice water emerge as a competition between the two components, each pushing towards its thermodynamically favoured state.

The physical confinement of water at the nanoscale can play a major role in controlling its properties, with fundamental implications in physical, chemical, geological and biological phenomena.^{1,2} Not surprisingly, the mobility of nanoconfined water along with its behaviour at interfaces has attracted widespread attention.³⁻⁵ In this regard, the nature of the interface and the geometric details of the confining surface are key parameters.^{6,7} In particular, confinement in the nanometre range can inhibit the arrangement of water molecules into an ice structure, and thereby prevent crystallization at subzero temperature and create a state of amorphous water.⁸⁻¹⁰

Confinement within soft interfaces, such as those formed by the self-assembly of surfactants in an aqueous environment, was suggested as a model for confined water in a cellular environment.^{6,11-13} Thus, understanding of the properties of water in such systems can provide key insights into the mechanisms of cell survival at low temperatures.¹⁴ In particular, confinement effects are reported in various phases formed by hydrated monoacylglycerols.^{15,16} The polymorphism of the most commonly studied monoacylglycerols at different hydration levels and temperatures includes lamellar (L_α), inverse bicontinuous cubic (Q_{II}), inverse hexagonal (H_{II}) and inverse micellar (L_2) liquid crystalline phases.^{17,18} Specifically, the L_α phase consists of stacked planar lipidic bilayers separated by slabs of water, in which the lipid tails have no positional order within a single layer, whereas the Q_{II} phases comprise a single curved lipidic bilayer arranged in three-dimensional space along continuous periodic minimal surfaces. Three distinct Q_{II} phases can be formed according to the surface symmetry: gyroid (Q_{II}^G), diamond (Q_{II}^D) or primitive (Q_{II}^P) and, in all cases, the lipidic bilayer is surrounded by two identical, but not interconnected, aqueous channels.¹⁹ In H_{II} , the lipids aggregate into

inverse micellar cylinders that are packed into a hexagonal lattice.²⁰ Among these geometries, cubic phases are of particular interest due to their unique properties, which include a solid gel-like consistency, transparency, high interfacial surface area and thermodynamic stability in excess water.²¹ These features, together with their ability to solubilize hydrophilic and hydrophobic guest molecules, render these biomaterials useful in various applications, which range from biosensors and drug delivery systems²² to catalysis.²³ Most remarkably, cubic phases are ideal matrices for the reconstitution,²⁴ stabilization and crystallization of membrane proteins.^{25,26}

Unfortunately, just below room temperature, the rich monoacylglycerol polymorphism is lost, as this common class of lipids crystallizes into a lamellar phase (L_c) in which the lipidic tails pack into a crystalline lattice that exhibits long-range order.²⁷ Furthermore, below 0 °C a coexistence of L_c with ice is found at all hydrations.¹⁷ This not only limits any practical use of lipidic mesophases at low temperature but also prevents the use of these systems to study the properties of subzero nanoconfined water, due to its occurrence as crystalline ice. Recently, however, we showed²⁸ that by replacing the cis double bond in the middle of the lipidic chain of the most-studied monoacylglycerol, monoolein, with a cyclopropyl moiety, a novel lipid monodihydrosterculin (MDS) is obtained, whose phase behaviour reveals the absence of the reverse hexagonal phase and the stability of the Q_{II}^D phase down to 4 °C. This feature is sufficient to facilitate, for example, membrane protein reconstitution and crystallization at temperatures as low as 4 °C, where standard monoacylglycerols are frozen into the lamellar crystalline phase L_c (ref.²⁸). The atypical behaviour of hydrated MDS at low temperatures is reminiscent of the ability of cyclopropanated phospholipids to enhance bacterial resistance to cold shock,²⁹ which suggests an effect of the cyclopropanation in stabilizing lipidic liquid crystalline phases at subzero temperatures.

Inspired by this favourable background and to investigate the phase properties of novel lipids with restricted geometries, we here introduce the design of a library of cyclopropyl-modified monoacylglycerols in which the rigidity of the lipidic tail can be modulated by

changing the number and the position of the cyclopropyl group, along with the length and the curvature of the hydrophobic chains. In this way, a new family of designer lipids is presented that form mesophases with unconventional properties at low temperature, the most remarkable being the capacity to confine glassy water down to at least 10 K, even with extremely slow cooling rates. Our study shows the presence of amorphous water in soft biomimetic interfaces at low temperatures and in quasi-equilibrium conditions.

Through a systematic study, based on small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), we elucidated the role of the rigidity of the lipid tail on the ensuing phase behaviour. Here we exemplify the versatility and the power of the approach on two cyclopropanated monoacylglycerols, taking their *cis* double-bonded homologues as a benchmark. Particular attention is given to the low-temperature phase behaviour of dicyclopropylmonolinolein (DCPML). In this system, the thermal behaviour of the confined water was investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), elastic and inelastic fixed window scan neutron scattering (FWS), wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) and NMR spectroscopy to reveal a system with unique low-temperature behaviour due to a subtle lipid-water interplay. This was complemented by molecular dynamics simulations, which allowed interpreting and addressing ice stability and water mobility within the lipid-confined geometries.

Lipidic polymorphism

To date, the number of natural lipids that form Q_{II} phases is limited, and most systems consist of hydrated isoprenoid lipids, unsaturated monoacylglycerols and a few synthetic lipids designed and synthesized by varying the head group.³⁰ The lipid chain provides the scaffolding element of all mesophases: its molecular structure, the specific length and position and degree of unsaturation, as well as curvature, greatly affect the structural properties of the ensuing mesophases.^{18,31}

Replacement of the *cis* double bond of monoacylglycerols with a chemically analogous *cis* cyclopropyl moiety maintains a similar chain curvature and lipid length, but results in a

substantial variation of packing frustration and lateral stress of the tails. The rigidity of the lipidic tail can be further modulated by changing the number and the position of the cyclopropyl groups, as well as the length and the curvature of the hydrophobic chains. In addition to MDS,²⁸ the cyclopropanated lipids monolactobacillin (MLB) and DCPML, analogues of monovaccin (MV) and monolinolein (ML), respectively, were synthesized (Fig. 1a and Supplementary Fig. 1). The full binary phase diagrams for these designer cyclopropanated monoacylglycerols were established by SAXS, and are shown in Fig. 1b,c, overlaid on the corresponding phase diagrams of the olefinic monoacylglycerols.¹⁸

Figure 1: **Phase diagrams of cyclopropanated monoacylglycerols MLB and DCPML.** **a**, Chemical structure of the two olefinic monoacylglycerols MV and ML and of their cyclopropanated homologues MLB and DCPML. **b**, Sample composition-temperature phase diagram of the MLB:water system (solid lines) overlaid on the phase diagram of the MV system. **c**, Sample composition-temperature phase diagram of the DCPML:water (solid lines) overlaid on the phase diagram of the ML system. The background phase diagrams in **b** and **c** are adapted from Kulkarni et al.¹⁸

Hydrated MLB presents a transition sequence similar to that of classic monoacylglycerols (Fig. 1b and Supplementary Fig. 3), in which L_α , Q_{II}^G , and Q_{II}^D are observed on increasing levels of hydration. In contrast to MDS,²⁸ the highly curved H_{II} phase is present in MLB at high temperature. The H_{II} phase and the Q_{II}^D cubic phase were found to be stable in excess of water, and it was possible to determine a full hydration line for both phases through the

analysis of the lattice parameters at each level of hydration (see Supplementary Fig. 2).

In the case of the most curved lipid in the series, DCPML, a most remarkable and unusual phase behaviour was observed (Fig. 1c and Supplementary Figs. 4 and 5): the Q_{II}^G cubic phase readily formed at 22 °C with a water content as low as 5% (w/w). The phase sequence on hydration from Q_{II}^G to H_{II} was markedly different from that of the most common sequence of phases for monoacylglycerols ($L_{\alpha} \rightarrow Q_{II}^G \rightarrow Q_{II}^D$). Previous studies showed that pure hydrated monoacylglycerols can form H_{II} only at high temperatures. Stable H_{II} phases at room or physiological temperature require the addition of hydrophobic molecules^{32,33} or the presence of an ether rather than an ester bond linking the head group to the lipidic tail.³⁴ The characteristic slow molecular release from H_{II} makes this geometry particularly appealing for several applications, such as drug delivery^{35,36} and membrane protein reconstitution,³⁷ but the complexity of ternary systems has limited the popularity of this mesophase.

Formation of the H_{II} phase at room temperature suggests a shift of the DCPML phase diagram to lower temperatures and hydration, which was confirmed by a dedicated investigation. A DCPML sample with 12.5% w/w water was first cooled in a stepwise manner to -20 °C and then heated back to 22 °C. At the end of each step in both directions, the system was equilibrated and SAXS profiles were collected (Fig. 2a). The phase transition from L_{α} to Q_{II}^G occurs between -15 and -10 °C in both the heating and cooling directions, and reveals a novel stable lipidic cubic phase at subzero temperatures. As expected, the water channel radius of the Q_{II}^G phase decreases on heating from a maximum of 8.4 Å at -10 °C to 7.8 Å at 22 °C (Supplementary Table 2). The stability of the Q_{II}^G cubic phase at subzero temperatures is remarkable, and is in contradistinction to all the other lipids that are known to form cubic phases, such as monoolein, which crystallize in a lamellar crystalline phase and ice below 0 °C (ref.¹⁷).

Water behaviour

The liquid crystal nature of DCPML at subzero temperatures suggests non-trivial features of the water confined in the nanochannels. The size of the water regions (slabs or channels) can be tuned by changing the water/lipid ratio (Supplementary Table 2). Melting transitions were studied by DSC measurements of the mesophases at various hydration levels (Fig. 2b). Samples of DCPML were treated thermally in a heat/cool/heat cycle from $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a scanning rate of $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. The traces presented in Fig. 2b were obtained during the second heating process. A sharp ice melting peak at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, characteristic for pure water, appears in the samples with 25% and 20% w/w water. As hydration is lowered, the peak first broadens (15% w/w water) and then completely disappears in the samples with 5% and 10% w/w water. Therefore, confinement within the L_{α} and Q_{II}^G phases in the low hydration regime is strong enough to completely prevent water crystallization at the considered cooling rate. This result is in line with previous work, in which the impossibility of ice nucleation under extreme confinement was ascribed to the need of the formation of a minimal ice nucleus of radius 1 nm (ref.³⁸). Moreover, confinement effects were reported in the range between 1 and 100 nm (ref.⁹), in addition to extremely reduced mobility in pores with diameters between 4 and 50 Å (ref.³⁹). The small peaks observed at higher temperatures in Fig. 2b correspond to the transitions between different geometries, and are in line with the SAXS results (Fig. 1c). The deviation of a few degrees in the transition temperatures can be explained by different heating rates and subsequent equilibration time, as well as an error ($\pm 1.5\%$) in the sample composition (water) given the different batches of lipids. The absence of ice for temperatures as low as $-60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is a unique feature of DCPML; ML at similar compositions always shows the transition peak for ice formation (Supplementary Fig. 6). This confirms that confinement alone is not enough to prevent water crystallization, but rather that it acts synergistically with the liquid-crystalline behaviour of the lipids.

FWS measurements (Fig. 2c,d) were employed to confirm the absence of a first-order transition in DCPML with a low water content. In bulk water, the mobility changes abruptly

Figure 2: **Low-temperature phase studies of water confined in DCPML mesophases.** **a**, SAXS profiles of DCPML mesophases that contain 12% (w/w) water at selected temperatures. The phase transition from L_α to Q_H^G occurs between -15°C and -10°C . **b**, DSC traces of DCPML with water content that ranges from 5% to 25% w/w. The peaks for ice melting occur in the samples with 25% (olive green), 20% (magenta) and 15% (blue) w/w water, and are absent in the samples with 10% (dark red) and 5% (orange) w/w water. **c,d**, Temperature-dependent neutron elastic (**c**) and inelastic (**d**) scattering of the DCPML samples with 15% (blue) and 7.5% (red) w/w water, 15% w/w D_2O (light green) and ML 7.5% w/w water (black). The insets show the derivatives of the scattering intensity. The DCPML samples with 7.5% w/w water (red) and 15% w/w D_2O (light green) do not show any transition peak for water freezing, whereas the DCPML samples with 15% w/w water (blue) and ML with 7.5% w/w water (black) show transition peaks at -9°C and -8°C , respectively. The error bars are standard deviation of the counts. **e**, WAXS profiles at -30°C of a DCPML sample with 10% (dark red) and 25% (olive green) w/w water. The crystalline scattering pattern is absent in the sample with 10% w/w water, whereas a profile typical of hexagonal ice is obtained from the sample with 25% w/w water. The broad peak present in both profiles is characteristic for the L_α phase. **f**, Temperature dependence of the water diffusion coefficient D in the sample with 10% w/w water estimated by NMR spectroscopy. NMR spectra at different temperatures are reported in the insets.

at 0 °C, which results in a sudden jump in the neutron scattering intensity. The samples were cooled to -263 °C at a rate of 0.1 °C min⁻¹, equilibrated and subsequently heated at the same rate. Measurements were performed during the heating cycle. The sample with 7.5% w/w water was chosen to ensure a single geometry in the subzero temperature range (Supplementary Table 1). The FWS profiles show no jump around 0 °C, although a change of slope indicates an increased water mobility from around -50 °C. In contrast, when a mesophase with the same topology and water content is produced from the commercial ML instead of DCPML, water melting is clearly observed at around -10 °C, as evidenced by a sharp peak in the first derivatives (Fig. 2c,d insets). DCPML with 15% w/w water also shows a jump that corresponds to ice melting at around -10 °C. Nevertheless, in this case the intensity of the transition is smaller, which indicates that only part of the water is involved in ice formation, in agreement with DSC. Moreover, samples hydrated with D₂O instead of H₂O were employed to isolate the signal of the protonated lipid molecules, that is, the lipidic contribution to the overall mobility of the system. The lack of a jump for a lipid-lipid transition confirms the absence of the L_c crystalline phase in DCPML (Fig. 2c,d).

WAXS experiments at low temperatures reveal a hexagonal structure of the ice in the samples with 20% and 25% w/w hydration (Fig. 2e), as well as the absence of a crystalline arrangement in the WAXS region for the other samples, which thus further confirms the liquid crystalline nature of the lamellar phase (L_α) and, for low hydration, the absence of crystalline ice.

Water mobility and phase behaviour were also investigated by diffusion NMR spectroscopy (Fig. 2f and Supplementary Fig. 7). For the sample with 7.5% w/w water, the detection limit was reached at 0 °C, which indicates a diffusion coefficient D lower than 10⁻¹¹ m² s⁻¹ (the smallest value measurable with our NMR set-up), whereas for the sample with 10% w/w water, diffusion was observed until -11 °C. The quasi-linear dependence of D on temperature (Fig. 2f) confirms the liquid nature of water in the considered range of temperatures and, together with the FWS and DSC results, indicates a transition from

liquid to glassy water at lower temperatures.

Lipid and water behaviour dependence

By combining the data acquired by DSC, FWS, WAXS and NMR spectroscopy, the phase diagram of water confined in DCPML mesophases was established (Fig. 3a). The enthalpy peaks in the DSC and the intensity jumps in FWS were employed to draw the line at which water crystallizes into hexagonal ice as confirmed by WAXS. The transition between liquid and glassy water was determined by a combination of NMR spectroscopy and WAXS, respectively addressing the low mobility and amorphous structure of the water phase.

Figure 3: **Low-temperature phase diagram of the water and DCPML lipidic phase.** **a**, Subzero phase diagram of H₂O confined in DCPML mesophases based on DSC, neutron scattering, WAXS and NMR data. **b**, Subzero phase behaviour of DCPML determined by SAXS measurements overlaid on the phase diagram of the confined water.

These features are intimately related to the peculiarities that distinguish DCPML from all the other known monoacylglycerols, namely a general shift of the phase transitions to lower temperatures and hydration, and the absence of L_c even at extremely low temperatures. The steric hindrance of the cyclopropyl groups and the presence of several diastereomers that differ in the relative configurations of the two cis-cyclopropyl groups are understood to be the reasons that prevent the packing of the lipidic chain of DCPML in a crystalline phase.

The lipidic geometry at low temperatures was revealed by systematic SAXS measurements, and the results are shown in Fig. 3b overlaid on the water phase diagram. On hydration, a re-entrant transition $L_{\alpha} \rightarrow Q_{II}^G \rightarrow L_{\alpha}$ can be observed in the temperature range

between -10 °C and 0 °C. Remarkably, the presence of liquid water at subzero temperatures is associated with the stability of the Q_{II}^G cubic phase. When cooling down at low hydration, the combination of lipid disorder and geometrical confinement of the L_α phase (for example, DCPML with 7.5% w/w water at 0 °C has water slabs of thickness 3 Å) prevents ice formation at any temperature.

In contrast, increasing the hydration leads to the formation of hexagonal ice on cooling. On cooling the sample with 20% w/w water to -30 °C, SAXS and WAXS showed that the Q_{II}^G phase is stable for hours, with no ice detected. The transition to L_α with a water layer thickness of 8.2 Å occurs after incubation for one hour at -40 °C, together with the appearance of ice peaks in the WAXS region. On heating from -40 °C, the L_α phase is stable until 0 °C. Between -40 and -20 °C, the lattice parameter a shows the typical decrease observed for mesophases (from 39.2 Å to 38.4 Å). In contrast, a increases between -20 °C (38.4 Å) and -10 °C (39.2 Å), which is usually associated with an increased hydration of the lipid bilayer. Remarkably, this temperature range corresponds to the onset of ice melting observed by DSC (Fig. 2b), and thus correlates the swelling to the progressive rehydration of the L_α phase. On transition from L_α to Q_{II}^G ($a = 110.2$ Å) at 0 °C there is no evidence of hexagonal ice. Although metastability of the lipidic phase has been observed in monoacylglycerols,¹⁷ the extraordinary hysteresis between cooling and heating in the samples in which ice is formed, together with the re-entrant lipidic phase behaviour, suggests a competition between the formation of ice and the stability of the cubic phase.

Molecular dynamics simulations

Our experimental findings were further supported by molecular dynamics simulations. To that end, a systematic study of ice melting and water mobility within L_α and Q_{II}^G geometries was performed.

We considered the mW force field, a coarse-grained model of water,⁴⁰ which has been successfully employed to address the features of supercooled water⁴¹ and ice melting in

cylindrical nanotubes^{38,42} (Methods). The lipid-water interface was represented as liquid water molecules forced to keep a disordered configuration at any temperature via harmonic springs.³⁸ This choice reflects the unique lipidic liquid-crystalline nature of DCPML at low temperatures, and ensures the hydrophilicity of the interface.⁴² Subsequently, the water domains were filled with liquid water and hexagonal ice in contact with each other (Fig. 4a,b). This set-up enables computation of the ice melting point T_m by systematic simulations at different temperatures T (ref.⁴³). If $T < T_m$, the ice nucleus propagates to the entire system, whereas for $T > T_m$ it melts (Fig. 4). T_m for hexagonal ice at various hydration levels was computed, for both L_α and Q_{II}^G geometries (geometric details given in Supplementary Table 3). The melting point under confinement is generally lower than that in bulk (Fig. 4d), in direct agreement with the DSC experiments. For a given geometry, T_m increases with the size of the confining region, in accord with previous reports on different systems.⁸ When comparing L_α and Q_{II}^G geometries with a similar water content, T_m is systematically lower in the latter case, which thus points to the existence of a temperature range in which only L_α is compatible with the presence of ice.

A second set of simulations addressed the experimental observation of glassy water on transition from cubic to lamellar geometries by studying the mobility of liquid water inside the Q_{II}^G and L_α mesophases. To this aim, a system that contained only liquid water was quenched at temperatures between -50 and 0 °C. After a short relaxation, the average self-diffusion coefficient D of the molecules in the aqueous phase was computed, which gave the plots reported in Fig. 4e and Supplementary Fig. 8. The horizontal grey line indicates the liquid/glassy transition, whose value was arbitrarily fixed to $150 \text{ \AA}^2 \text{ ns}^{-1}$ for explanation purposes. This value is unusually large for real water, and is a consequence of the known overestimation of water diffusion by the mW model.⁴⁰ Three important features emerge from the results. First, for a given system, D increases as a function of temperature and shows a linear behaviour in the considered range. Second, for both L_α and Q_{II}^G , at any temperature the diffusion coefficient is smaller for more confined water phases due to the stronger pres-

Figure 4: **Molecular dynamics simulations of water and ice under confinement.** **a**, Representative snapshots of molecular dynamics simulations on the melting point of the lamellar mesophase at 54.3% hydration. Centre: Starting configuration, partially filled with ice (white beads) and liquid water (blue beads). Left: Final configuration below the melting point. Right: Final configuration above the melting point. The top and bottom rows give perspectives orthogonal and parallel to the hexagonal plane, respectively. In the bottom row, lipid-like molecules are depicted as orange beads. **b**, Representative snapshots of water confined within an Q_{II}^G cubic phase at 54.3% hydration, for the starting (centre) and final configurations below (left) and above (right) the melting point. To enhance visibility, the lipid-like molecules are not drawn. **c**, Time evolution of the fraction of liquid water for the same system as in **a**, both above (red continuous line) and below (black dotted line) the melting point. **d**, Simulated phase diagram obtained by combining the results for T_m within L_α (squares and dashed line) and Q_{II}^G (crosses), and the liquid-glass transition lines for L_α (black continuous line) and Q_{II}^G (red continuous line). **e**, Diffusion coefficient versus temperature for L_α at 8.9% hydration (full red stars), L_α and Q_{II}^G at 17.8% hydration (filled and open purple circles, respectively) and Q_{II}^G at 35.9% hydration (open magenta diamonds). The dashed purple line shows the path followed on cooling by the system at 17.8% hydration and indicates the sudden drop of D due to the lipid-lipid transition. The horizontal grey line denotes the chosen threshold to consider a system as glassy.

ence of bound water (Supplementary Fig. 11) and in agreement with previous experimental and theoretical observations.^{15,44} Third, mobility within Q_{II}^G is larger than that in L_α with the same hydration for water content below $\sim 35\%$ w/w, after which the trend is reversed (Supplementary Fig. 8). These results indicate that the lipid-lipid transition has a major impact on diffusion, and thus explain the simultaneous observation of a liquid-to-glass transition corresponding to the $Q_{II}^G \rightarrow L_\alpha$ order-order transition detected experimentally at low hydration (Fig. 3). Following this argument, in Fig. 4d we plot the liquid-glass transition lines based on the chosen threshold (Fig. 4e) for both L_α and Q_{II}^G . Due to the difference in mobility in the two phases (Fig. 4e), these two lines delimit a region in which water is liquid in Q_{II}^G and glassy in L_α (shaded region in Fig. 4d); in other words, water is certainly liquid above the shaded region, and certainly glassy below, inferring by diffusivity arguments that the $Q_{II}^G \rightarrow L_\alpha$ order-order transition is located within the shaded region. Indeed, precisely as for the liquid-glass transition lines, also the $Q_{II}^G \rightarrow L_\alpha$ order-order transition curve is known to possess a negative slope from both theory^{45,46} and experiments.¹⁸ Remarkably, the combination of the simulations on melting and mobility delimits a subzero region of liquid water and Q_{II}^G with the presence of a minimum in the temperature-composition diagram, reminiscent of a eutectic and in direct analogy with experiments (Fig. 3). The minimum predicted by simulations is located at coordinates (27%, -30 °C), not far from the experimental minimum (12.5%, -13 °C), given the necessary assumptions in the coarse-grained simulations (Supplementary Fig. 9).

The quantitative details of the results depend on the particular choices made, that is, the simplified force field, water-like interaction between lipid and water molecules, lipid-lipid transition line and the glass threshold. Nevertheless, their qualitative features are very robust and corroborate the experimental observations, which indicates the following physical picture. At low hydration, the system follows the ‘standard’ behaviour, that is, a transition line from cubic to lamellar with a negative slope (Figs. 3 and 4d).^{18,45} On cooling, the Q_{II}^G phase switches to L_α , experiencing a sudden drop in water mobility (Fig. 4e). The

lower mobility implies that the system requires more time to equilibrate. Therefore, in this regime the cooling process crosses the melting line (Fig. 4d) after diffusion has already been hampered, that is, prior to water crystallization, and thus results in the observation of glassy water (Figs. 3 and 4d). At a critical hydration, the lipid-lipid transition line crosses the lamellar ice-melting line. On further cooling beyond this point, the Q_{II}^G mesophase with highly mobile water enters a region of the phase diagram in which freezing is possible, but only within a lamellar arrangement. This induces a forced structural transition, and thus leads to a lipid-lipid transition that follows the T_m lamellar ice-melting line with a positive slope. These two different slopes are at the origin of the $L_\alpha \rightarrow Q_{II}^G \rightarrow L_\alpha$ re-entrant behaviour. This mechanism can be ascribed to the large difference in the enthalpy change of lipid-lipid and ice-water phase transitions, as evidenced by the DSC curves. For example, in the 20% profile (Fig. 2b), computation of the peak area at ~ 0 °C (ice-water transition) and at ~ 30 °C (lipid-lipid transition) yielded an 85-fold difference. Due to the large enthalpy difference, the system finds it thermodynamically convenient to switch geometry and let water freeze, although the barriers involved in such a major rearrangement can easily lead to the observed hysteresis.

Conclusions

In summary, we designed, synthesized and investigated a new library of monoacylglycerol-type lipids in which the naturally occurring cis double bonds were substituted by rigid cyclopropyl moieties, and thus prevented lipid crystallization. In this way, the rich polymorphism of lipidic mesophases is extended to subzero temperatures, which opens unexplored possibilities in the storage of amorphous water within soft biological interfaces. The most remarkable features enabled by such a lipid molecular design are the presence of liquid water down to -10 °C in the Q_{II}^G double gyroid cubic phase, and glassy water down to -263 °C in the L_α lamellar phase. These results expand our understanding of how two main components of life, that is, water and lipids, interact under extreme conditions of temperature and

geometrical confinement and highlight the crucial role played by the confining soft interfaces. Beside their fundamental significance, our findings may also open new perspectives and opportunities in the use of such tailor-made lipidic mesophases in low-temperature biomimicry, as well as in biochemical and biophysical investigations with a special emphasis on complex biomacromolecules that are unstable at room temperature.

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Author contributions

E.M.L. and R.M. designed and directed the study. L.S.M. developed the lipid synthesis, produced lipidic mesophases, performed SAXS and WAXS experiments, and coordinated the NMR, DSC and FWS experiments. S.A. set up and performed molecular dynamics simulations. M.D. synthesized, purified and performed NMR characterization of the lipids. J.J.V. performed DSC experiments. F.J. collected and interpreted FWS data. S.J. collected and interpreted diffusion NMR data. O.Z. directed the NMR studies. L.S.M., S.A., E.M.L. and R.M. wrote the manuscript with contributions from all the authors.

Methods

Cyclopropanated lipids were synthesized according to the procedure previously reported by Salvati Manni et al.²⁸ For both lipids the synthesis was accomplished in two steps, starting from the corresponding commercially available acid **1** (Supplementary Fig. 1). Cy-

clopropanation of the olefins was carried out with diethyl zinc and diiodomethane in the presence of 2,4,6-trichlorophenol at $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to afford cis-cyclopropanation derivatives of acids **2** in 69-71% yield; these were then reacted with an excess of glycerol in the presence of 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide and 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine in a mixture of dichloromethane and dimethylformamide to afford the desired ester **3** in 58-71% yield. The resulting synthesized monoacylglycerols were a mixture of all the possible enantiomers and diastereomers. Moreover, the natural transesterification of the head group of the monoacylglycerols created an equilibrium between the 1- and 2-isomers.

Purity of the lipids was confirmed by $^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (Supplementary spectra 1-8) and mass spectroscopy. Supplementary Information gives detailed synthetic procedures.

Mesophase sample preparation. Liquid-crystalline mesophases were prepared by mixing weighed quantities of the desired lipid and water (to achieve the desired composition for each sample of the phase diagram) inside sealed Pyrex glass tubes, followed by melting to a fluid isotropic state by gentle heating, mixing by vortex and centrifugation until a homogeneous mixture was obtained. The prepared mesophases were then allowed to cool to room temperature over a period of 24 h in order for them to reach a state of thermodynamic equilibrium before the SAXS measurements were performed.

An alternative method using two 100 μl Hamilton syringes loaded with the weighed quantities of lipid and water was also employed. After homogenization with the Hamilton coupled syringe set-up, the obtained mesophases were transferred to 2 mm quartz glass capillaries (Hilgenberg) between two layers of Teflon and sealed with a solvent-free two-component epoxy resin adhesive (UHU plus). The sample was then melted to form an isotropic fluid, and subsequently equilibrated at room temperature for at least 24 h before measurements.

SAXS measurements. SAXS measurements were employed to determine the phase identity, and identify the symmetry and unit cell parameters of the mesophases at the different conditions. Experiments were performed on a Rigaku SAXS instrument with a

MicroMax-002+ microfocused beam that was operated at a voltage and filament current of 45 kV and 0.88 mA, respectively. The Ni-filtered Cu K α radiation ($\lambda_{CuK\alpha} = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) was collimated by three pinhole (0.4, 0.3 and 0.8 mm) collimators and the data were collected with a two-dimensional argon-filled Triton detector. An effective scattering-vector range of $0.03 \text{ \AA}^{-1} < q < 0.45 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ was probed, where q is the scattering wave vector defined as $q = 4\pi \sin \theta / \lambda_{CuK\alpha}$, with a scattering angle of 2θ , calibrated using silver behenate. Quartz glass capillaries (2 mm) that contained the sample were placed into a stainless-steel holder.

Additional measurements were performed on a Bruker AXS Micro, with a microfocused X-ray source, that operated at a voltage and filament current of 50 kV and 1,000 μA , respectively. The Cu K α radiation was collimated by a 2D Kratky collimator, and the data were collected by a 2D Pilatus 100 K detector. An effective scattering-vector range of $0.04 \text{ \AA}^{-1} < q < 0.5 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ was probed. Samples were placed inside a stainless-steel cell between two thin replaceable mica sheets and sealed by an O-ring, with a sample volume of 10 μl and a thickness of ~ 1 mm. Measurements were performed at different temperatures and samples were equilibrated for 30 min prior to the measurements, whereas the scattered intensity was collected over 30 min. For the low-temperature experiments, special care was taken to exclude supercooling: samples were cooled down at a rate of 1 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ and equilibrated for 3 h at the lowest temperature. SAXS profiles were collected after sample equilibration for 30 min at each temperature, and then increasing the temperature.

Mesophases were identified by their specific Bragg peak positions. For the double diamond cubic phase (Q_{II}^D), the relative positions in q of the Bragg reflections are at $q = \sqrt{2} : \sqrt{3} : \sqrt{4} : \sqrt{6} : \sqrt{8} : \sqrt{9} \dots$, whereas for the gyroid bicontinuous cubic phase (Q_{II}^G) the Bragg peaks are at $q = \sqrt{6} : \sqrt{8} : \sqrt{14} : \sqrt{16} : \sqrt{20} \dots$. The H_{II} phase is identified by reflections at $1 : \sqrt{3} : \sqrt{4} \dots$, the bilayer lamellar (L_{α}) phase exhibits Bragg peaks in the ratio of $1 : 2 : 3 : 4 \dots$ and the L_2 phase is identified by a single characteristic broad peak. The mean lattice parameter, a , was deduced from the corresponding set of observed interplanar distances, d ($d = 2\pi/q$), using the appropriate scattering law for the phase structure. For

cubic phases:

$$a = d\sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2} \tag{1}$$

whereas for the H₂ phase:

$$\frac{4\pi}{q\sqrt{3}}\sqrt{h^2 + hk + k^2} \tag{2}$$

For the L₂ phase, which shows only one broad peak, d is termed the characteristic distance.

WAXS measurements. WAXS measurements were employed to determine the water crystallinity at different hydration levels and temperatures. Samples were prepared and handled as described for the SAXS measurements.

Experiments were performed on a Rigaku SAXS instrument with a MicroMax-002+ microfocussed beam that was operated at a voltage and filament current of 45 kV and 0.88 mA, respectively. The Ni-filtered Cu K α radiation was collimated by three pinhole (0.4, 0.3 and 0.8 mm) collimators and the scattered X-ray intensity was detected by a Fuji Film BAS-MS 2025 imaging plate system. An effective scattering-vector range of $0.2 \text{ \AA}^{-1} < q < 2 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ was probed.

DSC. DSC experiments were performed on a Thermal Advantage DSC from TA Instruments. The samples were loaded in aluminium capsules contained in a steel sample pan of known mass and thermal conductivity. The experiments were carried out with an empty sample pan as the reference. Samples were scanned at a scanning rate of $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in a heat/cool/heat cycle. They were first heated from room temperature to $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, then cooled down to $-70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, allowed to equilibrate for at least 48 h and subsequently scanned over a temperature range from -70 to $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Self-diffusion of H₂O by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy. Diffusion NMR was measured on a Bruker AV-III 500 MHz spectrometer equipped with a room temperature, z gradient BBI probe head using the stimulated echo pulse sequence with bipolar gradients and a

longitudinal eddy-current delay as found in the Bruker standard pulse-sequence library.⁴⁶ The diffusion time was set to 200 ms and the eddy-current delay to 5 ms. The apparent diffusion coefficient at each temperature was obtained by non-linear least squares fits of the water signal intensities found for 16 different magnetic field gradient strengths varying in a linear fashion between 2 and 98% of the maximum gradient strength (53.5 G cm^{-1}) to the relevant expression:

$$I(q) = I(0) \exp \left[-Dq^2 \left(\Delta - \frac{\delta}{3} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

with $q = \gamma g \delta$, γ is the gyromagnetic ratio, g the gradient strength, δ the total gradient pulse width of a bipolar gradient pulse pair, Δ the diffusion time and D the diffusion coefficient.

Neutron spectroscopy. Neutron spectroscopy (FWS) was used to measure the portion of static hydrogen atoms in the sample, and so as a complementary tool to detect phase transitions. The samples were cooled down from room temperature to $-263 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and data were collected during heating back to room temperature at the rate of $0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Neutrons scatter elastically on immobile atomic nuclei, whereas all type of motions, such as vibrations or diffusion, cause inelastic scattering of the neutrons. Therefore, at a finite temperature the intensity of the elastically scattered neutrons is reduced by the Debye-Waller factor, which accounts for thermal vibrations. For example, melting of bulk (or bulk-like) water is a first-order phase transition and would cause a sharp decrease of the intensity. The signal intensity is directly proportional to the number of immobile hydrogen atoms (other elements can be neglected for the present case). The sample is a mixture of lipids and water, which have nearly the same hydrogen density. The measurements were performed at the MARS spectrometer (SINQ, Paul Scherrer Institut) using an energy resolution of about $13 \text{ } \mu\text{eV}$. This corresponds to an observation time of about 100 ps; motions that are slower are not detected. Simultaneously to the elastically scattered neutrons, those with a small energy transfer ($20\text{-}60 \text{ } \mu\text{eV}$) are also recorded, which happens in the case of diffusion. The sample (150 mg) was distributed between two thin aluminium sheets ($15 \text{ mm} \times 50 \text{ mm}$) and enclosed

in an aluminium sample holder. The sample was perpendicular to the neutron beam. Data treatment (energy integration, background subtraction and normalization) was performed using an in-house script available at the instrument.

Molecular dynamics simulations. Simulations of the system were performed by means of the mW model.⁴⁰ In this force field, water is modelled as a four-valence element with intermediate properties between carbon and silicon, by means of a modified Stillinger-Weber potential. Each molecule is represented as a single bead subjected to two- and three-body potentials. We refer the reader to Molinero and Moore⁴⁰ for the exact formulation of the force field and the values of the parameters. As for the lipids, following Moore and co-workers,³⁸ we considered a configuration of liquid water within the region that corresponds to the lipid bilayer (a simple slab or a region that surrounds the minimal surface of a gyroid for lamellar and Q_{II}^G , respectively) and forced the system to keep such a configuration via harmonic constraints with an elastic constant equal to 30 kcal mol⁻¹. The region that corresponds to the lipid bilayer in the Q_{II}^G case was identified by means of the algorithm proposed by Assenza and Mezzenga.⁴⁴ All the molecules in the system interacted via the mW potential. The simulations were run in the NVT (constant number, volume and temperature) ensemble via a Nosé-Hoover thermostat with a relaxation time of 1 ps and an integration step of 10 fs.

To find the melting point, we adopted the approach from García Fernández et al.⁴³ by putting in contact a nucleus of ice and liquid water. Based on the WAXS measurements, we built the ice nucleus according to a hexagonal structure. In the case of the lamellar geometry, we chose to put the hexagonal planes parallel to the lipid-water interface, as it is the configuration that is expected to be most stable. In the case of Q_{II}^G , little influence is expected from the precise orientation due to the large orientational heterogeneity of the channels. The amount of ice and liquid water was monitored in time by means of the CHILL algorithm,³⁸ with the exception of the monolayer case, for which we considered the trigonal order parameter q_3 from Henchman and Cockram⁴⁷ and assigned to the liquid phase the

molecules that satisfy $q_3 < 0.995$. For each geometry and temperature, we ran simulations up to 10 ns. If in the majority of simulations the final number of molecules assigned to the liquid phase was larger than that in the starting configurations, the system was considered to be above the melting point; otherwise, it was below. As we proceeded with temperature steps equal to 5 °C, the final melting point had an indeterminacy of 2.5 °C (ref.³⁸).

Diffusion simulations were prepared in a similar manner, although in this case the water-containing region was simply filled with liquid water. For each temperature, the system was quenched and shortly equilibrated (0.1 ns), after which the average mean-square displacement ($\text{MSD}(t)$) was computed. For Q_{II}^G , the diffusion coefficient D was computed by fitting $\text{MSD}(t) = 6Dt$, and care was taken to consider MSDs short enough to ensure that the labyrinthic features of the network of water channels did not affect the computation.⁴⁴ For lamellar geometries, two different components along the plane of the slab ($\text{MSD}_{xy}(t)$) and in the transverse direction ($\text{MSD}_z(t)$) were considered. The former contribution was fitted by $\text{MSD}_{xy}(t) = 4D_{xy}t$, whereas for $\text{MSD}_z(t)$ the corresponding diffusion coefficient D_z was extracted via a formula that took into account subdiffusivity as described in Supplementary Fig. 10. The overall diffusion coefficient was then computed as $D = 2D_{xy}/3 + D_z/3$.

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